

D5.3 Data Protection & Impact Assessment

Data security and the ethical dimensions of the DIRECTED Data Fabric

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Executive Summary

This deliverable builds upon the high-level architecture of the Data Fabric which was initially laid out in D5.1. This document, D5.3, describes the data protection impact assessment and ethical aspects of the Data Fabric. It is written in conjunction with D5.2, where the low-level design of the Data Fabric is detailed, and D5.4, where the implementation plan and forthcoming documentation are rolled out. Therefore, several cross-references will be found among D5.1, D5.2, D5.3 and D5.4 all together documenting the preparations necessary to successfully implement, deploy and operate the Data Fabric in DIRECTED.

Since 2018 the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has become a fundamental regulation to protect natural users regarding processing of personal data. As a legal framework, it defines the tasks and responsibilities of data controllers and processors in order to actively ensure that personal data is used and processed in accordance with the informed user's consent. The focus for this deliverable is the data protection impact assessment (DPIA) which has to be conducted when storing and processing of personal data leads to a “high risk” for the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

In this deliverable, we illustrate how a DPIA can be carried out on the Data Fabric within the DIRECTED project. Here, the Data Fabric forms our virtualized environment where we can ensure compliance consistency either by organizational rules or setting technical safeguards. The deployment and operation of the Data Fabric is highly related to the actual protection of personal data in order to stay compliant with the GDPR. For this, technical and organizational measures have been applied to protect the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

Art. 35, GDPR requires a DPIA, when there is a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons at storing and processing their (personal) data. Conversely, for storing and processing low risk personal data, or just non-personal data, a DPIA is not required at all. For this reason, a prior DPIA for the Data Fabric as a pure technical environment only makes limited sense. Rather, the datasets that are actually uploaded and processed over time must be assessed under the given environmental and security conditions offered by the Data Fabric. An obvious exception here is the user's authentication data, which may come from an external identity provider and for which the Data Fabric offers integration points.

Within DIRECTED, different partners and stakeholders work together collaboratively on different kinds of data and processes to answer questions on Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA). Therefore, we strive to clarify under what

circumstances a DPIA is necessary, when it has to be conducted and by whom. The necessary technical measures are described in Section 2 and shall support the data controller in conducting the DPIA. Further, for a smooth adoption of the Data Fabric, usage guidelines, templates, and web forms must be created (especially for Data Stewards), which must be checked and consulted before uploading/processing data and stored as part of the metadata. Terms of use must also be drawn up to clarify the circumstances under which further processing of certain data is permitted or prohibited. To this end, the datasets themselves must contain information about such restrictions in their metadata.

The DIRECTED project addresses key ethical dimensions of the Data Fabric related to the use of data for natural hazard decision-making, including Human Autonomy, Agency, Liberty, Technical Robustness & Safety, and Transparency & Accountability. Designed to empower users with data and tools for informed decision-making, the Data Fabric ensures that decisions are made by the users, while the system remains open to future expansion through the integration of additional data and models. Ethical aspects are incorporated through training materials, metadata documentation, and in-system reminders, promoting continuous reflection on principles such as equity and the responsible use of data.

The system's security and resilience are prioritized with advanced authentication and authorization measures, continuous monitoring, and proactive vulnerability management. Leveraging open source technology, the Data Fabric benefits from rigorous community testing and regular updates to ensure robustness and reliability. Reproducibility and transparency are enhanced by documented workflows, clear versioning, and publicly accessible software, enabling users to trace and validate results.

The Data Fabric aims to improve stakeholder decision-making by making complex models more transparent and accessible. Expert users can access detailed scientific references, while novice users benefit from simplified explanations in the system's metadata. Furthermore, limitations and uncertainties are clearly documented to guide data selection and model use. Stakeholder engagement is promoted through targeted training and international dissemination efforts, ensuring a broad understanding of the system's capabilities.

Ultimately, the Data Fabric fosters a culture of compliance and ethical practice, guided by principles of transparency, accountability, and open science. By providing accessible, secure, and transparent tools, the project enhances the quality, reliability, and ethical use of data in addressing natural hazards. Therefore, it directly contributes to the DIRECTED goals of improving DRM and CCA measures.

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List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
API	Application Programming Interface
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
RWL	Real World Lab
S3	Amazon's Simple Storage Service
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction & Overview

1.1 Data Fabric

The development of the Data Fabric in the DIRECTED project offers tools and services for accessing, processing, and discovering geospatial data, with a specific emphasis on RWL use cases related to Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR). The developed prototype will be deployed in the Open Telekom Cloud, with data and processes provided by project stakeholders within the consortium.

The platform is very flexible, and may also process sensitive data that is protected by the GDPR. When data protection is evaluated, there are usually three core roles that are involved: The (natural) user, data controller and the data processor. The first two roles are filled by humans, the first one being the entity whose data is processed and the latter the one that owns the data. The Data Fabric will solely act as the data processor, processing the data while applying technical and organizational measures.

As the Data Fabric depends on human inputs, i.e., data is sourced externally and uploaded by humans, the Data Fabric will not be able to prevent threats such as data abuse by design. But it will raise awareness and provide meta information to critically question outputs (Deliverable 5.1, Section 2.5), as well as employing technical safeguards to define policies and rules to ensure compliance with best practices.

1.2 GDPR

As the Data Fabric may process and store sensitive data, data protection must be ensured priority. In the European Union this is mandated by law, with many requirements and processes being defined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). As a legal framework, it defines the tasks and responsibilities of data controllers and processors in order to actively ensure that personal data is used and processed in accordance with the informed user's consent.

This deliverable focuses on the Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA), as mandated by Article 35 of the GDPR, when there is a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons at storing and processing their (personal) data. These assessments ensure that sensitive data is handled appropriately, e.g., they ensure the processing happens on a lawful basis and appropriate measures are taken to protect the individual.

The Data Fabric takes somewhat of a special role, as it provides a relatively flexible framework for data and processes, without many restrictions on the possible data that is ingested and processed. As the assessment requires relatively detailed knowledge about the data, making a general assessment for the complete fabric is not possible.

An exception is the user's authentication data which is used for authentication and authorization within the Data Fabric, as this data is clearly defined and does not change depending on the current usage of the platform. But this data does not contain sensitive information about individuals that would impose a risk if exposed. A dedicated DPIA is therefore not required, but it should be ensured that the data is minimized, only stored as long as necessary as prescribed by Art. 6 GDPR and the users consented to the storage and processing of the information.

Technical security measures implemented in the fabric components themselves and organizational measures are to be defined as part of this document.

2 GDPR Compliance – Organizational Measures

Several organizational measures are taken to facilitate compliance with the GDPR concepts outlined above. Information about the measures must also be made available to the users, e.g., in the form of a Terms of Use. This must also include the purpose of the processing, i.e., explain the legitimate interest that may exist, and an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing

2.1 User Regimes and Access

The data fabric will accommodate different users with different responsibilities and accordingly different levels of access. In the following, the different Regimes are disseminated, examining the responsibilities of the user and the corresponding access.

2.1.0 Infrastructure Administrator

All components of the infrastructure are running in self-hosted infrastructure that needs to be maintained accordingly. Administrative tasks contain the management of the infrastructure itself, e.g., provisioning of virtual machines, provisioning of storage disks, as well as management of backups. As they control the infrastructure, they conceptually cannot be excluded from access to all data, including sensitive and user data. They should therefore be sensitized to the fact that the infrastructure contains such data and special handling is needed, e.g., the requirement for encrypted backups.

In this project, the role will be filled by 52°North.

2.1.1 Data Steward

Data Stewards are responsible for administering the research data. When creating resources, Data Stewards are therefore responsible for evaluating whether the data contains sensitive data and flagging the resource as such if true. If data is evaluated to be sensitive, a dedicated impact assessment is required. As the impact is fully driven by the specifics of the data, no general assessment is possible. More details are given in Section [2.2](#).

For assigning access rights to owned resources only non-personalized information (i.e., group membership) is used, Data Stewards do not have access to individual users.

Data Stewards might not be represented by a human being but can also be a software component such as a workflow or automated script. In this case, the responsibility lies with the steward that parametrizes and starts it.

During the DIRECTED project, Data Stewards will primarily be members of the RWLs, with assistance by 52°North.

2.1.2 User Administrator

User Administrators are responsible for managing users and their associated group memberships. The administrators will therefore be exposed to Personally Identifiable Information (PII). Additionally, as they control group memberships and can arbitrarily assign users to groups, they have access to all data. The user administration therefore needs to be assessed the same as the infrastructure administrators, they need to be sensitized about the presence of PII and the appropriate handling.

During the DIRECTED project, users will be managed centrally by 52°North.

2.1.3 Anonymous User

Anonymous users, users that have no authentication credentials, can only see data that is flagged as public. Data that is flagged as sensitive cannot be made public, accordingly, no GDPR-relevant data is exposed to the user.

2.1.4 Authenticated User

Logged-In users can read all data they are granted access rights on by the Data Stewards. This might include sensitive data, it must be ensured that the users are known to the system and that they are made aware of the sensitivity data they are accessing.

In the DIRECTED project, this role will be filled by members of the RWLs (hosts and selected stakeholders) and other project members without direct administrative tasks.

2.2 Workflows

As the evaluation of data protection lies in the border region between data controller and data processor, both are heavily involved in the corresponding workflows. The basis for this collaboration is usually a signed agreement between the two parties, which includes a list of technical and organizational measures taken by each party.

2.2.1 Data Protection Impact Assessment

The GDPR mandates safeguards and mechanisms to ensure GDPR compliance, such as a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) in the case of:

“Where a type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.” (Article 35 GDPR)

The probability that storing or processing of data in the Data Fabric would result in a “high risk” for the rights and freedoms of natural persons is presumed to be low, but cannot be neglected. The assessment clarifies for each dataset whether the probability exists, and ensures that proper measures are taken to prevent the processing of such data if no sufficient measures are available. This section clarifies when DPIA has to be done by whom and how technical and organizational measures help to conduct the assessment once it becomes necessary.

As different measures need to be taken depending on the result of the DPIA, special storage is required, or strict access restrictions need to be imposed. Assessing the data after it has already been uploaded into the Data Fabric is insufficient. The assessment needs to be performed before the data ever enters the fabric infrastructure. The assessment will therefore be integrated into the workflow for uploading the data, i.e., the upload is only possible after the assessment has been made.

To support the Data Steward in assessing whether and what measure must be taken, a central questionnaire is developed based on the list of criteria suggested by the Data Protection Working Group 29^{1,2} for assessing if data is “high risk”. Factors that facilitate a high risk are:

- the existence of assessment or scoring operations,
- the presence of automated decision-making,
- systematic monitoring,
- the use of special categories of data,
- the existence of large-scale data processing,
- matching operations between different databases,
- personal data relating to vulnerable individuals,
- the use of new technologies,
- the fact that the processing may inhibit the data subject from either exercising their rights, or using a particular service.

This questionnaire will be realized as a web form and be an integral part of the data registration and upload process. The results will support the Data Steward in appropriately flagging the dataset’s sensitivity for use in the Data Fabric. The results of the web form will also become part of the dataset’s metadata.

As the Data Fabric does not limit the processing of data to a single scope, personal data must not be processed arbitrarily, but only in dedicated workflows. If these workflows augment or alter the data, a new DPIA might be required. As this fully depends on the individual process, the Data Steward is responsible for evaluating whether the combination of a specific process with specific data is critical, and triggering and providing a new DPIA.

As the DPIA can only be performed with in-depth knowledge about the data, automating the assessment or delegating the responsibility to a central authority is not feasible. The responsibility for providing an assessment therefore lies with the Data Steward that is actively uploading the data to the platform. The specific steps that are required depend on the data, but are guided by Article 4 of the GDPR and may include the following steps:

- Consultation with the designated Data Protection Officer
- Potential engagement with data subjects or their representatives^{2,3}
- Evaluation of potential risks to data subjects' rights and freedoms

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/611236>

² https://gdprhub.eu/Article_35_GDPR

³ https://www.dsgvo-portal.de/gdpr_article_35.php

- Analysis of the likelihood and severity of identified risks^{2,4}

Enforcement of these guidelines are handled by technical measures, specifically the Data Steward is required to provide a DPIA (or alternatively explicitly state that no such assessment is necessary), and if so is required to fill out the appropriate web form before any upload is possible. The form itself is based on the Template provided by the UK's Information Commissioner's Office⁵ and is directly integrated into the relevant components.

⁴ https://www.dsgvo-portal.de/gdpr_article_35.php

⁵ <https://gdpr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/dpia-template-v1.pdf>

2.2.2 Rights of the data subject

The GDPR reserves the rights for a subject to interact with the stored data about it in Articles 12 to 23. This includes for example the right of access, right to rectification or right to erasure. All of these measures are very dependent on the data itself and require collaboration with the data controller, they are therefore difficult to define for all possible Data Fabric installations. It is therefore delegated to the roles of *user administration* and *Data Steward* described in the previous Sections [2.1.2](#) and [2.1.1](#) respectively.

For the actual data that is processed in the Data Fabric, the task of handling such requests is delegated to the responsible *Data Steward* (Section [2.1.1](#)). Only the Data Steward can give accurate information, correct the data or delete the data on request. As the data is provided directly by the RWL, workflows must exist inside the RWLs that allow for such a workflow and can handle requests.

For all data that is not part of the research data, i.e., data that is used internally for management purposes such as login information, the *user administration* (Section [2.1.1](#)) is responsible. As this role is fulfilled exclusively by 52°North staff in the DIRECTED project, the existing workflows for data privacy and protection affairs at 52°North are reused ([Privacy Statement](#)⁶).

⁶ <https://52north.org/privacy-statement/>

3 GDPR Compliance — Technical Measures

As described in [Section 1](#), technical measures should be implemented to facilitate the protection of sensitive data. The two core technical measures are a strict separation of GDPR-relevant data and unrelated data into separate storage infrastructures, and the general hardening of the infrastructure to ensure that no unauthorized access bypassing the technical measures exist.

3.1 Data Storage

To ensure appropriate data protection for the different types of data, different storage providers are used. Three types of data with different protection requirements are differentiated:

1. General Data

General data comprises the bulk of the data and can be classified as all data that is non-sensitive, i.e., data that has no additional restrictions for protection and does not contain any PII. This data therefore does not have a high impact in regard to the GDPR. In the Data Fabric architecture, local storage on the hosts themselves or network storage using private S3 Buckets is used, depending on the specific circumstances. There is no required segregation of different datasets, all data can be stored in a common folder structure.

2. Sensitive Data

Sensitive data contains PII or otherwise sensitive information and therefore needs to be protected. The impact of a data breach cannot be assessed in general, as it is dependent on the content of the data, e.g., its topic and granularity, and therefore needs to be assessed for each dataset individually. Workflows for this assessment are described in [Section 2.2](#). To ensure that there is no accidental breach of data, it must not be stored together with non-sensitive data. In the Data Fabric, the data is therefore exclusively stored in encrypted storage using dedicated private S3 Buckets or dedicated local disks. If the data is backed up, backups are also ensured to be sufficiently encrypted using up-to-date encryption standards.

3. User Data

User data inherently contains PII and therefore requires special protection. As the user data stored is solely used for simple authentication, only low sensitivity data is needed, such as names and email-addresses. The impact of a breach is therefore assessed to be low. The Identity Provider used for User Authentication across the Data Fabric uses its own dedicated datastore/database, which is completely separated from the rest of the infrastructure. There is no mixing of this user data with research data at any point. Access to this data is limited to the Identity Provider, there is no access to the datastore from any other component of the Data Fabric. This is also reflected in the architecture design, where the Data Fabric consists of two core parts for authorization and data handling (comp. Figure 8 in Deliverable D5.2).

3.2 Access Control

As described in detail in Deliverable 5.2 Section 2.7, the Data Fabric employs access control for all components of the Data Fabric via a centralized service. This ensures appropriate protection of data and allows for central management of access rights by the user administrators. The access policies on user level are also enforced for model chains. Refer to Deliverable 5.2 for details about the architecture design.

3.3 Infrastructure Hardening

Besides the technical measures that are integrated into the components of the Data Fabric itself, several additional measures are taken to ensure the Data Fabric can operate securely in a productive environment.

3.3.1 Firewall

To allow for monitoring and controlling, all incoming and outgoing network traffic is routed via a firewall. As most infrastructures already provide a firewall (or comparable component), e.g. a general company firewall, it is not explicitly modeled in the Data Fabric itself. It is assumed to be provided by the hosting infrastructure and configured according to common best practices. The deployment and user guides of the Data Fabric will encourage the contributing parties (i.e., RWL) to set-up and maintain a firewall if not yet present.

In the DIRECTED core infrastructure, a firewall is deployed in the Open Telekom Cloud that routes all network traffic and protects the components.

3.3.2 Automated Security Scans

As new vulnerabilities are discovered constantly, deployed components should regularly be updated and their vulnerability to published security issues monitored. To ensure that this is not missed, automated security scans are performed on all deployed components.

This is implemented using the Trivy Vulnerability Scanner and the Trivy-Operator, both working together to scan all deployed components of the Data Fabric daily for known vulnerabilities. When components are presumed to be affected, automated alerts inform the administrators about the need for an update or other relevant action.

3.3.3 Penetration Tests

While the technical measures protect the infrastructure when correctly configured, misconfigurations, e.g., S3 Buckets that are public instead of private or APIs which are missing authorization, can occur. Specifically, S3 buckets are very vulnerable to misconfigurations, and in the last three years there have been several high profile cases where private data was leaked accidentally as buckets were readable without authentication.

To ensure that there are no misconfigurations, penetration tests will be performed internally by 52°North. Due to scope constraints, penetration tests by external organizations are not possible in this project, but should be considered if project software is further developed to reach productive technical readiness level.

4 Ethics

As the Data Fabric is designed to process data on natural hazards for regions affecting numerous people, several ethical dimensions emerge that need to be addressed. Following the [SHERPA guidelines](#)⁷, the following aspects are relevant for the Data Fabric and will subsequently be discussed.

4.1 Human Autonomy, Agency and Liberty

The Data Fabric provides means of connecting data and tools and to visualize information products for decision-making. However, no methods are developed in the Data fabric that directly take decisions. The decisions are always taken by the user, which the Data Fabric informs to the best of its capabilities. The agency of users is limited by the choice and availability of data, models and defined scenarios that are implemented in the Data Fabric. As the Data Fabric is widely based on open standards, additional data and models can generally be added to the Data Fabric and lower the limitations of the (expert) users' agency. However, the process of adding new data and models requires technical and thematic expertise and can only be done by selected user roles (i.e., Data Steward, [Section 2.1.1](#)). However, the actually integrated tools will always only be a subset of data and models available. Connecting them in the Data Fabric will already improve the liberty of stakeholders compared to current siloed systems. Making results available through the Data Fabric to the wider public also allows questioning the outputs and enables citizens to approach stakeholders. Ideally, the Data Fabric shall also suggest including additional resources into a decision process.

As the system itself cannot ensure a responsible use of the Data Fabric, we will raise ethical aspects in training material, but also integrate them into the system. When adding new resources to the Data Fabric (through the Data Steward), there will be an accompanying web form where questions regarding GDPR but also ethical aspects are raised (see [Section 2.2.1](#)). The responses are documented in the metadata of the newly added resource and help to classify the data. While using the Data Fabric, ethical reminders specific to the data sets and models will pop up and remind the user of the principles to reflect on, e.g., loss of lives and

⁷ <https://www.project-sherpa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/use-final.pdf>

equity respecting minorities. There will also be a *good practice recommendation* for users delivered through the Data Fabric, that will highlight the key ethical aspects to consider before using the Data Fabric and communicating the results in a jargon free practical wording. Those recommendations might be split to different phases of the use of the Data Fabric in order to not overload the user and only remind of currently relevant information. The information presented shall also contain links to further reading/training. The attributes to trigger these ethical reminders as pop-ups or inline are collected during the registration of a data set accompanied by the aforementioned web form. Hence, ethical aspects are not only covered in onetime training material, but become also apparent while using the Data Fabric. However, the resources of the Data Fabric can also be used via APIs, where awareness can only be raised through the metadata accompanying those services. In the training material for this step of the resource creation, there will be additional information to raise awareness of the GDPR and ethical aspects.

4.2 Technical Robustness and Safety

To ensure that the Data Fabric is secure and resilient against attacks, the project will implement a comprehensive security strategy based on multiple robust measures. It will integrate advanced authorization and authentication solutions to ensure that access to sensitive data is tightly controlled (comp. [Section 3.2](#)). This will significantly reduce the risk of unauthorized access and potential breaches.

The Data Fabric utilizes the latest, state-of-the-art software components maintained by the open source community. Hence, the Data Fabric will benefit from cutting-edge technology and best practices in security. Open source solutions often undergo rigorous community-driven testing and auditing, further enhancing their resilience.

Establishing continuous monitoring of core components will allow swift detection and response to potential vulnerabilities or abnormal behaviors. This proactive approach will help in identifying and mitigating threats before they can impact the system. During DIRECTED, 52°North acts as operator of the Data Fabric and will receive alerts and take action.

Regular backups and Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines will support the system's resilience by ensuring that data and configurations can be quickly

restored or redeployed in case of an incident. This setup will enhance both data availability and recovery capabilities.

By frequently updating base images and components, we will mitigate the risks associated with outdated or vulnerable software versions, aligning with best practices for software security. Establishing automated tests using open source solutions like Trivy will regularly scan for vulnerabilities, allowing the project to promptly identify and address potential risks and take action.

During the project period, 52°North will be responsible for managing any failures that occur within the Data Fabric. Should a failure arise, 52°North will promptly react to resolve the issue and may involve other project partners as needed to address more complex challenges. Given that the Data Fabric will be deployed primarily in a prototype setting rather than an operational environment, any failures are expected to have a low impact on the overall functionality and operations.

After the project's conclusion, the responsibility for managing failures will shift to the individual operator of the Data Fabric. The operator will be in charge of ensuring the system's resilience, addressing any failures, and maintaining the Data Fabric's safety and stability in a production environment. This transition ensures that long-term management and support of the Data Fabric will be handled by the entity responsible for its ongoing use and operation.

The Data Fabric is designed based on recent tools and developments from peer-reviewed research, ensuring that it leverages the latest, scientifically validated methodologies to deliver reliable and high-quality results. Test workflows will be developed to verify that the output of the Data Fabric remains consistent with the expected results, as established by the expertise of the model developers. These test workflows will regularly check the system's performance and accuracy, confirming that it continues to function as intended. In order to achieve some degree of reproducibility, each workflow run will be documented and stored as part of the metadata for the results published through the Data Fabric. This metadata allows users to trace and reproduce analyses performed by the system, enhancing reliability and transparency. While the Data Fabric's outputs will be reproducible as long as the input data remains unchanged, variations may occur if the external data used in analyses is later altered. These strategies will contribute to achieving a high degree of accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility of and within the Data Fabric.

4.3 Transparency & Accountability

A combination of openness and structured versioning will provide a robust framework for tracing the evolution of the system. All software developments will be open and publicly accessible, allowing for transparent tracking of changes (via a dedicated [GitHub repository](#)). Each release will follow a systematic versioning approach, enabling clear identification of updates and modifications over time.

The DIRECTED project aims at achieving a meaningful level of explainability of the Data Fabric. Given the complexity of many models, achieving full explainability can be challenging. However, to provide insights — particularly for experts in the field — the project will reference relevant scientific publications associated with each model. This will allow expert users to understand the theoretical foundations and assumptions underlying the models. Novice users can access additional information and explanations in simplified form that is contained in the metadata of the datasets and models. This shall enable citizens to understand the type of data and of models (e.g., hydrological simulation, economic loss model, cost-benefit analysis). Expert users will also have the flexibility to apply different models to the same task or re-run a modeling chain with slightly modified input data and publish those for review or open discussion. This capability will allow users to observe variations in outputs and better understand the dependencies and relationships within the modeling workflow, enhancing transparency and interpretability of the system's results.

Data and models naturally inherit uncertainties and limitations in their accuracy. To the degree this is known and quantifiable, the metadata of data and models will provide a section detailing the limitations and constraints for the specific data or model. This information will be accessible during data and model discovery in the Data Fabric, allowing the user to base the data selection and workflow composition also on uncertainty and accuracy aspects.

The DIRECTED project will effectively communicate the relevant functions of the system to stakeholders through a combination of targeted training and widespread dissemination efforts. Stakeholders (i.e., RWL hosts and members) will have access to training sessions designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the system's key functions. These sessions will ensure that stakeholders can effectively use the system and are well-informed about its capabilities. To reach a broader audience, the project will conduct announcements and

dissemination activities on an international level, targeting relevant groups and communities. This will increase awareness among stakeholders and promote engagement with the system across different regions and professional networks.

Auditability of the Data Fabric is supported through the achieved degree of reproducibility described in the previous section. The ability to publish model runs and outputs publicly also enables citizens and stakeholders to approach the Data Fabric operator or relevant local stakeholders with their questions and concerns.

In DIRECTED, a culture of compliance and ethical practice is rooted in our commitment to adhering to good scientific practices, ensuring rigor, transparency, and accountability throughout our research process. We prioritize reliance on open data and open source Software, which aligns with the principles of Open Science. Utilizing open source software encourages collaboration and knowledge-sharing within the community, allowing others to contribute to and improve upon our work. By using open data, we make our research processes more transparent, enabling validation and scrutiny by the scientific community and stakeholders. This openness supports reproducibility and helps to prevent issues related to data bias or hidden methodologies, fostering trust and credibility.

5 Conclusion

GDPR compliance is affected by a diverse collection of factors and cannot be achieved without collaboration by data controllers and data processors alike.

While this document gives general guidelines for compliance, it can only provide generic advice as the specificities depend on the actual data and processes and is therefore only available during the actual usage of the Data Fabric. This deliverable is therefore not an exhaustive list, but a set of measures that must be taken in any case accompanied by workflow descriptions that will be part of the Data Fabric supporting GDPR. It also addresses general data protection and sensitivity aspects.

The fabric itself can only deploy a very limited number of technical measures, aiming to make the process as easy as possible for the data controllers/stewards. But especially the DPIAs conceptually require collaboration by data controllers/stewards. To ease the process, an integrated tooling will be developed for the web front-end of the Data Fabric that facilitates DPIA and enriches the metadata of any resource.

Different ethical dimensions of the Data Fabric, Human Autonomy, Agency and Liberty, Technical Robustness & Safety and Transparency & Accountability, have been identified, and mitigation measures have been developed to address those. The Data Fabric enhances decision-making by connecting data and tools, empowering users with informed insights without directly making decisions. User agency is shaped by available data, models, and scenarios, though the open standards allow for future expansion. Ethical considerations are integrated into the system through embedded reminders, metadata documentation, and ongoing best-practice recommendations. This approach ensures that an ethical reflection is an ongoing part of the user experience. The Data Fabric is built on a secure, resilient, and transparent foundation, incorporating state-of-the-art open source technology and robust security measures to protect against unauthorized access and vulnerabilities. By embedding reproducibility, documented workflows, and scientifically validated methodologies, the Data Fabric aims to deliver reliable, high-quality outputs, supporting accuracy and transparency throughout its lifecycle. By prioritizing explainability and providing tailored insights for both experts and novice users, the project enhances understanding of complex models and data within the Data Fabric.

Annex I

Deviations from the Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement also lists the aspects of “endpoint security, privilege and identity assurance” for this deliverable. Those concepts are specific to the previous partner QOMPLX who had to step-back from the project on very short notice and were replaced by the 52°North GmbH. As the design of the Data Fabric is now different and open by design, it does not build upon proprietary solutions of QOMPLX. Hence, the above-mentioned aspects from the grant agreement are not relevant anymore and therefore not discussed in this document.

Partners

